

DELIVERABLE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a short overview of the production of all print and presentation materials for the communication and dissemination of SMART-electron. The first and second release of these assets are presented. All future printed materials for SMART-electron will be based on the designs and templates described in this document. Graphic materials play a key role in dissemination and communication, as the first impression one gets of the project, which cannot be undone, is imparted by them.

This document comprises four chapters.

Chapter 1 is a short introduction.

Chapter 2 provides a brief overview of the philosophy behind the design of the graphic materials.

Chapter 3 provides a list of the designs that were produced and details how the design and copywriting process unfolded.

Chapter 4 provides low-resolution copies of the first release of the designs.

Chapter 5 provides low-resolution copies of the second release of the designs.

Chapter 6 sums up the conclusions and take-home messages that were gleaned through this work.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS AND THIS DELIVERABLE?

Within SMART-electron the dissemination and communication materials are tools that will be used by:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Particularly by the staff responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, as this is a public document and is available on the project's website, it will be accessible by external parties interested in disseminating and communicating SMART-electron.

This deliverable will be updated periodically at a later phase of the project according to the project's needs.

2 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

The design of the printed materials was based on two simple but effective requirements: starting from the existing project logo, and tweaking the project website if necessary, we aimed to attain a graphic identity that is at the same time *distinctive* and *classic*. The branding guidelines as given in D6.3 were also drafted with this two-fold goal in mind. Achieving both a degree of timelessness and a striking design that 'speaks to everyone' has in turn two significant consequences.

A timeless and classic look means that the design is conceived to 'age well', which is one of QED's priorities given the fact that the project website, together with the graphic assets it contains, are required to stay up for at least 5 years after the end of project - which means no less than 9 years in the future.

On the other hand, a strong graphic statement that is simple, easy to identify, and based on universal proportions (such as for instance certain mathematical ratios) allows the use of the same design/theme for both dissemination and communication. This strong visual identity was consistently 'declined' in the various graphic & print designs, as detailed in chapter 3.

Both considerations translate into cost and labour savings for the project, especially with a view to its future upkeep/sustainability.

Another cost-saving consideration was the idea of designing templates for brochures and posters that the partners will be able to easily fill in and print locally as the need arises (see below).

2.1 NEW - FURTHER CONSIDERATIONS FOR THE SECOND RELEASE

The overall philosophy didn't change for the second release of the graphic assets. One of the main concerns was ensuring that they will cater for the needs of SMART-electron's upcoming 2023 International Conference. So we sought to maintain continuity with the previous designs, whilst bearing in mind the practicalities of the upcoming events. This gave rise to some interesting changes, detailed in chapter 3.3.

3 LIST OF THE GRAPHIC ASSETS THAT WERE PRODUCED

In terms of graphic materials for dissemination and communication, the needs of such an ambitious project as SMART-electron are many. Broadly speaking, some printed assets are meant to be general-purpose, i.e. deployable anywhere without any changes, whilst others are event-specific, i.e. tailored to each specific SMART-electron International Conference or event. Based on the project schedule as well as on an evaluation of the overall progress so far (and in particular on D6.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan), the following assets were thus identified and then designed:

1. foldable two-sided general-purpose square Project brochure;
2. template for conference-specific A2 Project poster;
3. general-purpose 80x200 Project vinyl banner;
4. template for the A4 Project conference programmes;
5. general-purpose SMART-electron-branded tote bag;
6. template for SMART-electron slides;
7. favicons and social media icons/banners;
8. graphic design guidelines;

9. NEW - novel colour scheme and layout for the conference-specific A2 Project posters;
10. NEW - designs for the conference-specific A4 book of abstracts, according to the new colour scheme
11. NEW - novel colour scheme and interior design for the foldable two-sided general-purpose square Project brochure;
12. NEW - Web banner for the upcoming International Conference.

1) General-purpose two-fold square brochure, to be deployed at various events as a general presentation of the project. The choice of a square format is due to reasons of compatibility with the square aspect ratio favoured for online assets (Instagram, browser favicons, shortcut icons on mobiles, etc.).

2) Template for event-specific vertical A2 poster, printable as A3 if necessary. The choice of a standard ISO 216 / DIN format instead of more 'fashionable' ones translates into savings for the project and in no way diminishes the impact of the design. A2 was chosen as the largest possible format that can be hung without too much trouble in pinboards and public spaces – since, trivially, a larger format guarantees greater visibility. The design is compatible with printing in A3, which is significantly cheaper for small runs of digital prints.

3) General-purpose 80x200 standalone vinyl banner, to advertise and signal events taking place in a specific venue, such as conferences, seminars, lectures, press conferences, etc. The choice of PVC as the printing material makes the roll-up banner suitable for outdoor use as well.

4) Template for the event-specific A4 conference programmes, which provides readers with the schedule for all the topics of all the talks and all the posters presented at the conference, as well as a list of all participants. It is also meant as a memento of the conference for all participants.

5) General-purpose SMART-electron-branded tote bag, to be given to all conference participants as well as to guests.

6) Template for SMART-electron slide presentations. To be used by all partners when presenting on behalf of SMART-electron. A set of coherent graphic rules is given in the template.

7) Browser favicons and social media icons & banners were derived from the logo and optimised according to the various social media guidelines.

8) Graphic design guidelines for the correct deployment of graphic assets (including the Logo) were produced in the form of a PDF booklet, which was distributed to partners.

9) The new colour scheme and layout for the A2 poster is aimed at facilitating fast and convenient printing by Project partners, thus providing value for money. The poster can be printed as A3 if necessary.

10) The new design for the conference-specific A4 book of abstracts will allow the collection and easy browsing of all the contributions to the SMART-electron 2023 International Conference.

11) The new colour scheme was also used for the re-design of the general-purpose two-fold square brochure, which is now harmonised with the new Conference printed assets.

12) A new Web banner was designed and placed on the Project website homepage, in order to promote the 2023 International Conference.

Insofar as possible, SMART-electron designs will be printed locally by partners, close to where they are meant to be deployed, in order to save on expenses and environmental impact. The designs are sent to partners with specific instructions as to the type of printing process, paper, and finish to be adopted, so as to ensure a consistently high standard of quality.

All the designs were optimised for offset printing but can be output as high-quality laser or inkjet prints if necessary.

3.1 THE ACTUAL DESIGN PROCESS

Work on the designs for SMART-electron's printed materials was conceived from the outset to evolve based on the graphic design done previously for the project: from the outset, we sought to expand as a coherent whole the system of typesetting and design rules underlying the project's graphic identity. Hence, starting from the existing logo and website (described in D6.1 Project Logo and Webpage), two different concepts were developed and explored.

The first one consists of evoking photons and electrons through the stylisation and extensive repetition of the S and the E in the project logo. The curved elements of the S and the straight elements of the E can in fact be thought of as corresponding to the photon and electron lines in Feynman diagrams. This dichotomy is appropriate for SE, which is all about shaping electron matter waves by using photons. At the same time, the curved and the straight element can be viewed as symbolic of the wave/particle duality which is one of the defining features of Quantum Mechanics.

The second concept revolves around the idea of the correspondence between theory and experiment. The inspiration for this was a figure in the 2018 Nature Communications paper on attosecond control of free electrons by Vanacore et al¹.

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-018-05021-x.pdf>

The starting point for the 'theory vs. experiment' concept for the graphic assets:
 the plots in <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-018-05021-x.pdf>

In the figure, the theoretical prediction for the light field amplitude vs. electron energy loss plot for the light-electron interaction is compared with the plot obtained through measurement. Since the interplay between theory/simulation and experiment is at the very heart of physics, we thought of applying an analogous graphic stylisation to the SMART-electron logotype, whereby the smooth predictions of theory are symbolised by the anti-aliased, vector-graphics version of the SMART-electron logotype, whereas the pixelated and noisy outcome of experiment is represented by the same logotype with added spatial distortion and rasterised with large pixels.

Early sketches for the poster (L) and the vinyl banner (R) based on the 'theory vs. experiment' concept

The same dichotomy was exploited for the inner fold of the brochure, where the two plots from the above paper mirror one another, with the symmetry about the vertical axis broken by the theory-vs-experiment discrepancy.

As to the use of colour, we followed our custom of relying on strong contrasts and simple colour schemes. In particular, we sought to build on the palette we chose for the website - by adopting the lime yellow we used for the webpages and logo, as well as its complementary colour for selected elements, such as the inner fold of the brochure:

Two early versions of the inner fold of the brochure based on the 'theory vs. experiment' concept and using the colour complement to the lime green of the Logo

In terms of paper formats, for speed of print and best value for money, we adopted standard DIN formats whenever possible - for example for the A2 poster for events. The brochure and the vinyl banner are an exception to our self-imposed "DIN-only" rule: we opted for a square brochure with a single inner fold due to reasons of compatibility with the square aspect ratio used in Instagram, as well as for browser favicons and link icons on mobile platforms. Having a unified design for all these assets -Instagram posts, favicons, mobile icons- makes a lot of sense since the SMART-electron presence across platforms is more immediately recognisable this way. The vinyl banner has a custom aspect ratio due to the brand-specific aspect ratio of the available blanks on which it is printed.

In the end, the first 'wave vs. particle' concept was deemed more impactful and won over the second one, which only survives in the inner fold of the brochure. Having settled on the main concept and proportions, special care was taken in considering the interplay of the designs with the type of paper and of printing method intended for each of the assets/formats. Then we proceeded to consistently 'decline' the leitmotiv in the various designs, which are shown in the next chapter. Throughout the design phase, all the guidelines regarding the use of the various official logos were observed.

3.2 COPYWRITING

Similar considerations of simplicity and efficacy were adopted for the copywriting. The latter, insofar as possible, eschewed lingo in favour of clear and simple explanations, understandable by the general public, but also providing meaningful information for specialists. The text can be read from the second figure in the next chapter.

3.3 NEW - FURTHER DESIGNS FOR THE SECOND RELEASE

New designs for some of the conference-specific A2 poster, the A4 book of abstracts cover, and the square brochures were conceived for the upcoming SMART-electron International Conference. The general requirement was that -whilst in line with existing graphic assets and rules- the new designs should be able to stand out in 'crowded' places, such as billboards and pinboards. We found that introducing an element of colour in the main *leitmotiv* of the posters and covers satisfied this need, whilst allowing a neat form of colour coding for the three remaining Project events:

The new designs for the A4 book of abstracts for the SMART-electron 2023 International Conference

The underlying SMART-electron colour scheme for print was also reversed, switching from white over black to black over white. This choice makes printing easier and cheaper for the hosting partner, enabling them to print the new designs directly with laser on inkjet printers, if necessary. This facilitates things, since large black surfaces are best printed via proper offset printing, or, better still, printed on black paper via hot stamping or screen printing; all these options are more expensive than direct printing on one partner's own printer.

Another decision we took in order to ease printing requirements was to employ a colour that is vivid but still within the standard CMYK and RGB gamuts used for printing. The Project thus retains its standard fluorescent palette for the website and for other online or non physical assets, whilst employing black, white, and primary yellow for printed, conference-specific graphic assets.

The foldable two-sided general-purpose square Project brochure was updated according to the new colour scheme. The Project logo in the brochure was left in its black version, so as to signify the general-purpose nature of the brochure. This has the added advantage of enabling a single print run for the brochures for all future conferences.

A Web banner advertising the next International Conference was added to the Project website. The choice of photo and of layout was done so as to attract prospective physical participants, who might be interested in the beauty and cultural sights of the Conference location.

All the above choices contribute to providing value for money.

Low-resolution copies and images of the new designs are provided in chapter 5 of this same document.

4 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (FIRST RELEASE)

The SMART-electron two-fold brochure

The SMART-electron vertical A2 poster, which is also the template for event-specific posters

The SMART-electron vinyl banner

The SMART-electron vinyl banner

*The SMART-electron template for conference programmes
(outer cover)*

The SMART-electron tote bags

Templates for SMART-electron slides

SMART-electron browser favicon (L) and Facebook/Whatsapp group icon (R)

SMART-electron Springboard icon next to those of the [Q-SORT](#) and [MINEON](#) EC projects

SMART-electron Facebook banners

Select pages from the SMART-electron graphic design guidelines booklet

5 NEW - LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF THE DESIGNS (SECOND RELEASE)

The new design for the SMART-electron International Conference poster

The new design for the SMART-electron International Conference poster

The new SMART-electron book of abstracts cover

New SMART-electron book of abstracts internal pages

The new SMART-electron two-fold brochure

The new SMART-electron 2023 International Conference banner

6 CONCLUSIONS

We think the results show the benefit of involving a professional media production company with the right profile in the design and copywriting process.

Suitable 'buffer time' needs to be scheduled between completion of the designs to the coordinator's and designers' satisfaction, and their final delivery. This is in order to take into account possible changes at the request of partners or of those institutions whose logo is included in the design. The number and duration of these 'refinement iterations' can be assumed to grow with a power law with the number of partners involved.

Further suitable buffer time should be factored in for checking printed samples ahead of each print run: the correct rendition of text, logos, and graphics/colours should be checked, as well as the quality of the folding in the case of the brochures.

In addition to general-purpose stand-alone banners and tote bags ready for any event, now the Consortium has conference-specific A2/A3 posters, A4 book of abstract designs, and square brochures. These printed assets complement the non physical graphic assets: the Project website, its favicons, Springboard icons, social media group thumbnails, and conference-specific Web banner.

Partners now have all these assets and templates at their disposal, so that they can start planning the printing of their own posters and brochures.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
1 UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO-BICOCCA	ITALY	UNIMIB
2 ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE EPFL	SWITZERLAND	EPFL
3 FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE CIENCIES FOTONIQUES	SPAIN	ICFO
4 TECHNION - ISRAEL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	ISRAEL	TECHNION
5 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ITALY	CNR
6 HOLOEYE PHOTONICS AG	GERMANY	HOLOEYE
7 QED FILM & STAGE PRODUCTIONS LTD	UK	QED

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL